

Lab tips, tricks and hacks: Etching SiO₂ without HF

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Etching of silicon oxide (SiO₂) is a crucial step in many nanofabrication recipes and is used to remove material in a precise and controlled manner. This process is essential for creating nanoscale structures that are used in a variety of applications, including electronics, photonics and biotechnology. However, the most commonly used etchant for SiO₂ is hydrofluoric acid (HF), which is an extremely dangerous chemical.

HF is a colorless and transparent fluid that resembles water, making it difficult to detect and handle. The transparency of the fluid makes it difficult to see when it has wetted a surface, which increases the risk of accidental exposure. In addition to its handling difficulties, HF is also very poisonous, highly irritating and corrosive. HF is fatal if inhaled, if swallowed, or in contact with skin. It causes severe skin burns and eye damage. The effects may be delayed after exposure.

Given the dangerous nature of HF, a safety training before starting to manipulate this chemical is mandatory, in order to learn the protective measures and the steps to follow in the event of an accidental spill. These protective measures includes wearing protective clothing, such as gloves and eye protection, and using fume hoods to prevent inhalation of the fumes. Moreover, it is important to follow proper disposal procedures to minimize the risk of accidental exposure and ensure the safe disposal of the chemical. Finally, working with HF alone, without anybody in a close lab room, is not recommended.

In our lab we have found that glass etching creams such as Armour Etch can be used as a safer alternative to HF and offer several advantages over traditional etching methods. According to www.whatsinproducts.com, Armour Etch contains: barium sulfate (0-6%), sulfuric acid (0-9%), ammonium hydrogen difluoride (21-27%) and sodium bifluoride (7-12%). The web does not specify the remaining components.

One of the primary benefits of using glass etching creams is their consistency (see Figure 1). These creams are very viscous and white, which reduces the risk of

spill and accidental exposure. Unlike HF, which is a clear and transparent fluid, glass etching creams are much easier to see and handle, making them a safer alternative for nanofabrication processes.

Figure 1. Etching SiO₂ on a SiO₂/Si substrate using glass etching cream. (1) SiO₂/Si chip and Armour Etch etching cream. (2) A plastic stick is used to scoop a bit of etching cream which is viscous and white. (3) A drop is placed in the center of the SiO₂/Si chip and stays stable because of its viscosity. The sample can be moved, handled with tweezers, even flipped upside-down without the cream falling off. (4)-(5) Once the etching is finished it can be easily washed away with water. (6) The etching cream only etches the SiO₂, stopping at the Si layer.

In addition to their consistency, glass etching creams can also be handled with common laboratory gloves without the need for additional protective equipment. This makes them a convenient and accessible option for nanofabrication processes, especially for those who do not have access to specialized equipment or training in working with hazardous chemicals like HF.

It is important to note that while glass etching creams are a safer alternative to HF, they are still toxic chemical substances and should be handled with care. It is advisable to wear protective gloves and work in a well-ventilated area to minimize the risk of accidental exposure.

We have characterized the etching rate of our Armour Etch etching cream. Figure 2 shows a test SiO₂/Si chip with 1100 nm thick SiO₂ layer that has been masked and subjected to etching process in increasing times: 20 s to 180 s. The optical image picture shows 9 squares with different apparent colors, corresponding to the different etching times. These colors occur due to the constructive or destructive interference of the optical light beams reflected at the air-SiO₂ and the SiO₂-Si interfaces.¹

Figure 2. Test SiO₂/Si chip to determine the etching rate.

Optical picture of a SiO₂/Si that has been masked with a vinyl mask to expose nine squared areas to the etching cream. Different exposure times were used ranging from 20 s to 180 s to determine the etching rate.

The thickness of the SiO₂ film can be accurately determined by reflectance spectroscopy.² By fitting the resulting reflectance spectrum to a multi-media optical system considering the different optical media (air, SiO₂ and Si) refractive indexes using the thickness of the SiO₂ layer as fitting parameter one can determine the thickness with high accuracy (± 1 nm in most cases). The SiO₂ and Si refractive indexes datasets can be downloaded from databases like <https://refractiveindex.info/>. Figure 3 shows examples of differential reflectance spectra acquired on regions of the chip subjected to different etching times.

Figure 3. Examples of differential reflectance spectra acquired on regions etched over different times. The figure compares the differential reflectance spectrum measured on the unetched SiO₂/Si chip and on regions etched for 60 s, 120 s and 180 s. All the plots include the experimental data (black) and the resulting fit to the Fresnel law based model using the SiO₂ thickness as fitting parameter. The SiO₂ thickness value that yields the best fit is displayed in each plot.

From the quantitative analysis of the differential reflectance spectra one can extract the thickness of the SiO₂ film after being etched for a given time. By plotting those results together, we can extract quantitatively the etching rate. Figure 4 shows the SiO₂ film thickness as a function of the time exposed to the etching cream. A linear fit of the dataset provides the etching rate from the slope: etching rate = 3 nm/s. Note that the etching rate of the etching cream might change with aging, an early etching rate characterization in our lab right after opening the bottle gave us a rate of 5.6 nm/s.

It should be stressed that the etching cream only etches the SiO₂ and stops when reaching the Si layer underneath (natural etch stop layer). This cream is thus useful to fabricate via contacts to the Si. We have used this feature of the etching cream in the past to fabricate a PN junction made with TiS₂ (n-type) and Si (p-type).³

Figure 4. Determination of the etching rate. SiO₂ film thickness as a function of the time exposed to the etching cream. A linear fit to the dataset gives the etching rate that is ~3 nm/s.

We have used the Armour Etch cream in combination with optical lithography to create custom patterns in SiO₂/Si chips. Figure 5 shows an example of a crosshair pattern, fabricated with this approach of photolithography and etching, used to facilitate finding flakes of 2D materials which is particularly useful when samples are fabricated in one lab and sent to other lab to be measured.

Figure 5. Example of pattern created in a SiO₂/Si substrate by optical lithography and etching with Armour Etch.

After etching we have observed often some debris on the etched surface. We found that [Hellmanex III](#) works very efficiently in removing them.

Figure 6. After etch cleaning. Optical images of 9 μm diameter SiO_2 pillars fabricated by optical lithography and etching with Armour Etch. Right after etching the sample is covered with debris that can be effectively removed by cleaning with Hellmanex III.

In conclusion, we have shown that SiO_2 can be effectively etched away using glass etching creams such as Armour Etch. These creams are safer than traditional etching methods, are easier to handle, and can be used with common laboratory gloves. However, it is still important to handle these creams with care and follow proper safety procedures.

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